

Impact of Company Branding On Consumer Product Preference in Automobile Industry an Empirical Study of Pakistan

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Abstract

This research study is based on the impact of company branding on consumers product preferences in automobile industry an empirical study of Pakistan. In this study five dimensions of company branding as Company name, Company image, Company reputation, Company loyalty and Company social responsibility were used. We made the hypothesis that all these dimensions have significant impact on consumer's product preference and we support these hypotheses through review of literature. For data collection we divide the Lahore city into nine strata and divide the questionnaires in offices and banks of each division. For analysis of the data we used co- relation and then regression analysis between dimensions of company branding with dependent variable of consumer product preference. After analysis we find that the three dimensions named as Company name, Company image and Company social responsibility has significant impact on dependent variable of Consumer product preference while the rest of dimensions Company reputation and Company loyalty do not have significant impact on Consumers product preference. The overall model demonstrates that company branding has significant impact on consumer product preference in automobile industry of Pakistan.

Key Words Company Branding, Company Name, Company Image, Company reputation, Company Loyalty, Company Social Responsibility, and Consumer Product Preference.

Introduction

About hundred years ago, no of thoughts that made logic formed the modern point of view on buying. In olden days, people bought things by spending money and that actions were named as buying and that were taken just to satisfy their needed products either goods or services. But now days, buying decisions are not taken by considering those measures like simply buy the product according to need. Presently, buyers buy things to remunerate themselves, to fulfill mental needs or to make themselves feel great. Currently, purchasers purchase things in light of the fact that they are lavish. They purchase things to create an impression, to show off their identity or to support their respect toward oneself (Goss 2006).

Consumer's product preference behavior can be explained by different purchasing patterns. Every consumer has a different understanding about his purchase of products. A consumer's purchasing pattern is made and developed during the life of the customer, or can be spur-of-the-moment and based on feelings of consumers. The purchase pattern the consumer's shows have different usage purposes. Consumer's purchase decision is also affected by consumption values. The consumption values explain the reason that why they chooses a particular product, which type of the product is more appropriate and adaptable for a particular consumer, and why they choose to purchase the product they use in their daily routine. There are number of factors which explain the purchase decision making: functional, social, emotional, epistemic, and conditional (Sheth, Newman et al. 1991). Consumer's purchase decision making depends on approach to the product and what consumption values he or she keeps.

Corporations are moving from a market or product focus to customer or consumer focus reveals the marketing evolution. As an effect to this prototype shift, corporations are continuously investing huge sums of money into understanding the consumer's product evaluation under the influence of company branding (Achrol and Kotler 1999). To support the consumer's decision making process of product, a company brand provides a shorthand device for their product preference and selection decisions (Kariuki and Karugu 2014).

In this research, as we are concerned about the impact of company branding on consumers product preference in automobile industry of Pakistan so we discuss some history of automobile industry. Since the time of independence of Pakistan the automobile industry was actively growing but not anyone automobile industry of Pakistan was prominent in worldwide. In Pakistan some automotive industries started with the collaboration of local industry and joint venture such as Toyota, Honda, Suzuki and general motors. After the independence of Pakistan in 1953 the first automotive plant established in Karachi his name was national motor limited which assembled the Bedford automobiles. Different auto industries assembled their cars in Pakistan started in different years as Suzuki in 1984, Toyota in 1993, Honda in 1994, Daihatsu and Hyundai cars assembled in 1999 (Information on History of Pakistan). In 2007 the total contribution of automobile industry in GDP was 2.8% which is increase up to 5.6% for next five to six years (Pakistan Automotive manufacturer Association: PAMA).

In the prior research studies, the concept of company branding has been discussed and analyzed by many researchers i.e. (Urde 2003), (Leitch and Richardson 2003), (Balmer, Harris et al. 2001), (Balmer and Gray 2003), (Martin, Beaumont et al. 2005), (Ahonen 2008) all of them point out that company branding is a vital issue for companies to address. However, few researches have inspected the dimensions of company branding and so there exists a research gap; we need to make a scale for company branding. Although Balmer, Mukherjee et al. (2006), Balmer, Harris et al. (2001), have tested the impact of various dimensions of company branding on consumers product preference but none of them added the dimension of company social responsibility in company branding which consumers considers while making judgment about company (Ricks Jr 2005). Secondly, all these researches conducted in east Asian nations like Taiwan and Japan but none is conducted in south Asian nation like Pakistan.

The objective of this study is to investigate the relationship and link between company name, company image, company reputation, company loyalty and company social responsibility with consumer product preference in selecting the cars among different company brands through a randomly and rigorous survey of consumers in scattered Lahore region who are belonging in different sectors. Particularly, we intend to answer the following questions

- Does company name influence the consumer product preference in automobile industry in Pakistan?
- Does company image influence the consumer product preference in automobile industry in Pakistan?
- Does company reputation influence the consumer product preference in automobile industry in Pakistan?
- Does company loyalty influence the consumer product preference in automobile industry in Pakistan?
- Does company social responsibility influence the consumer product preference in automobile industry in Pakistan?

Although other factors (such as country of origin and product brand name) are referred to have some impact on consumers' product preference, the scope of the current research is confined to the examination of company branding. The remainder of the paper is composed of four major sections. The second section deals with a brief review of company branding dimensions research (Company name, Company image, Company reputation, Company loyalty, Company social responsibility). The third section of the paper proposes a conceptual framework that helps understand the relationship between the different company branding dimensions and analyze the interplay between company name, image, reputation, loyalty and social responsibility. The fourth

section is designed to empirically test the proposed hypotheses. Finally, we conclude with a brief summary of the study's limitations and some recommendations for future research.

Literature Review

Few years ago, the impact of company branding on consumer product preference has gotten a limited consideration but, now a days as multinationals are progressively moving from the product branding to company branding Kowalczyk and Pawlish (2002), researchers are steadily giving careful consideration to the impacts of company branding on consumer product preference (Olins, Herrmann et al. 2000). As our current research study is confined to investigate the impact of company branding dimension on consumer product preference, we divide the concept of company branding into five sub-constructs: the company name (CON), the company image (CIM), the company reputation (CRE) the company loyalty (CLO) and the company social responsibility (CSR). First we elaborate the concept of consumer product preference.

Consumer Product Preference

Consumer product preference or product choice is interchangeable words which mean that to identify the consumer choice of product among different brands. Consumer product preference is associated with product brand loyalty, which means repurchase again and again by long period of time (Ghose and Lowengart 2013). Consumer behavior based on fully research about the cars, interiorly and externally design, features, model, brand name image, reputation, loyalty, price, availability of accessories, social responsibility and durability etc and after that purchase decision has to be taken (Partha and David 1994).

People want that products which have innovativeness and novelty with passage of time and change the style look, and feature, interior and exterior decorate according to fashion which used in current era for competitor brand. In china and west countries consumer used latest branded products with updated fashion and novelty with great features. Most of the researcher said that the new and advanced technologies with great features was high turnover in advanced nations and then import the developing countries from advanced nations (Zhou, Arnold et al. 2010). Brand name used in auto industry such as in Japanese auto brands Toyota, Honda, Daihatsu more popular in China, Middle East, Asian and European countries and some consumers have company brand loyalty to purchase only same brand again and again. Brand loyal consumers stick on oneness brand and convinced or advocated to others to use the same auto brand (Zhou, Arnold et al. 2010).

Decision making process based on the seeking information which attained and combined the information from various sources by external and internal resources to make a decision to choose a car over different options of companies (Schmidt and Spreng 1996). Before decided to purchase the specific company automobile firstly to get the necessary information which help in the decision making process. Consumer didn't buying any automobile either they know about automobile information particularly related to company of automobile (Formisano, Olshavsky et al. 1982). Some barriers faced by consumers to attain the information about automobile company performance and organized the information to understand in mind memory. Before purchasing we set the information in our mind and analysis it than take the step to interpret it and finally took the decision to buy a specific car (Johnson and Russo 1984).

Most of the consumers preferred foreign company brands that shown the ethnocentricity occurrence while the local automobile industry and economy of the nation threaten due to consumer emotionally attract with foreign made product described in many past researches. The ethnocentricity of consumer shown the personal and individual attitude and shows their affection with foreign automobile companies (Sharma, Shimp et al. 1995).

Company Name

The sub-construct, company name (brand) Kowalczyk and Pawlish (2002), measures how generally known the company brand is and to what degree this influences the consumers' product preference. Schultz and De Chernatony (2002) stated company brand name as "a collection of practical experience and emotional beliefs of consumers' which he shares with others". According to Gefter, Margulies et al. (1977) it is the sum of all the ways a company manages to recognize itself (i.e. company name, logotype, image, graphic system) to all its consumers.

By making groups of functional and passionate qualities for their brands, firms can include worth to the lives of consumers' (Vallaster and De Chernatony 2005): Consumers for the most part don't make associations with individual products or services; instead he or she does with a brand of a company (Venkatesh, Morris et al. 2003). Since long, organizations have recognized the influence of using the company name as master brand in the east. The accepted concept for the company brand is the company brand name (Balmer and Gray 2003). The corporation is a solid candidate for a brand as it carries reliability, genuineness, ethics, and expertise that inclined more consumers to purchase the company products. (Balmer, Harris et al. 2001) holds that company brand encourages consumers' craving to look deeper into the company and assess the way of the firm it works. Belief in the products and brand the firm offers incline clients to acknowledge its claims about different products and administrations.

Company branding has gotten more consideration from both professionals as well as scholars. Ward and Lee (2000) He found a shift from dependence on product brands to company brands. Others have additionally found that the use of company brand name seems to be more effective for the firms to attract new consumers and retain the current consumers (Balmer and Balmer 2001). Jo Hatch and Schultz (2003) Infer that organizations that have become successful in creating a company name (brand) are more aggressive than firms depending just on product brand in the today's markets made by globalization. Then again, company branding is additionally more intricate than product branding in that it requires synchronous and successful association of vital vision, hierarchical society, and images through which consumer attracted towards it. Dawar and Chattopadhyay (2002) stated that multinational firms from advanced nations ought to adjust to the economic situations in developing markets to effectively take advantage of these businesses. In this manner, a few inquiries emerge: which branding technique, company branding or product branding, do firms like to use in their starting entrance in the developing markets so that the consumers attracted towards the company. However, expanded administration levels and decreasing brand dedication describing today's commercial centers have prompted company branding turning into a key marketing tactic because now a days consumers focuses more on company name rather than the product brands of company. (Morsing 2002).

Company name (branding) empowers firms to utilize the vision and trend of the association expressly as a feature of its uniqueness (Balmer, Harris et al. 2001). Balmer, Harris et al. (2001) Calls for firms to in company their key vision with their brand building. Balmer, Harris et al. (2001) Characteristics the surge of company branding to the increasing expenses of publicizing, retailer power, item discontinuity, new item advancement cost efficiencies, and consumer's desires of company testimonials. Company name (brand) can build the company's discernibility, recognition and popularity to a more noteworthy degree than product brand. Balmer and Gray (2003) Keep up that one of the profits of solid company brands is that financial specialists may look for them out deliberately. They besides offer more risks for key or brand unions, and assume an imperative part in the recruitment and maintenance of significant representatives. Company marking/branding includes numerous consumers, stakeholders associating with various staff over numerous offices in an association (Mitchell 1999). Powerful company branding/marking obliges steady messages around a brand's character and uniform conveyance overall stakeholder gatherings to make a great brand notoriety and reputation.

On the basis of following explanation we conclude the hypothesis that

Ho: Company name does not have a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

H1: Company name has a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

Company Image

The second sub-construct that is identified with the company branding is the company image, which shows the general impression made on the personalities of people in general about the company (Gotsi and Wilson 2001). A decent company image can absolutely influence a company's business and piece of the overall industry (Shapiro 1982) and the foundation and support of a faithful association with consumers (Nguyen and Leblanc 2001). Company image is the sum total of impressions, imitations and expectations about a company developed in the personalities of its consumers and people in general (Phan, Yang et al. 2003) As expressed in the recent past, whatever you done and how you accomplish it makes an image (Marconi and Hunt 2003).

Wallin Andreassen and Lindestad (1998) report that company image serves as a paramount variable impacting the view of value, buyers' assessment of fulfillment and client reliability de Wetzels, De Ruyter et al. (1998) express that the company image is a data signal that consumers utilization to judge matters, for example, believability, saw quality and buy plans. A positive word of mouth is a building block in creating a positive image in the minds of consumers, as it leads to inclined more consumers towards the company products (Westbrook and Oliver 1991). An ideal brand image would have a positive impact on purchaser conduct towards the brand regarding expanding devotion, ordering a value premium and creating positive word of mouth. Recent studies contend that brand image is an imperative element influencing brand value. Likewise, Faircloth (2008) found that the more positive the brand image, the more consumers are eager to pay and subsequently the more prominent the brand value (Krishnan 2005).

Aaker (1996) He stated that a brand can be used as a yardstick to differentiate the company products from its major competitors by means a set of positive consumer observations and perceptions. As per both Kelly (1998) and Sharp (1995), numerous firms have understood that a solid company brand image can play a vital role in the in the presence of other strong competitors. So, if companies want to enhance the powers of its brand they require building a positive impression in the eyes of consumers for firm. Regardless of the absence of experimental confirmation, there is some understanding that a decent company image can decidedly influence a company's business and enhance the share of the company in market (Shapiro 1982). A decent company image leads to the foundation and maintenance of fully committed and loyal relationships with clients (Nguyen and Leblanc 2001).As reported by Keller and Hosany, Ekinici et al. (2006), a solid company image can be utilized to expand correspondence effectiveness and the message of the firm can be effectively delivered to the targeted audience. Restuccia and Rogerson (2008) He contended that company image can influence consumer conduct and behavior towards the company products. Balmer and Wilkinson (1991) He stated that a solid company image is the best type of product separation in order to attract consumers.

Whoever your client or consumer is, everyone follows up on the premise of what he or she have seen, heard and learned and everyone has his or her own particular image of your association. After every connection with your organization the waiting affiliations and impressions together structure the image of your organization (Argenti and Druckenmiller 2004).

A decent image can have an impact on product deals and the general picture of the organization (Huang, Swanson et al. 1991). Organizations producing goodwill by frequently tuning in philanthropy on the other hand reason related occasions regularly make a positive image and positively impact the consumers (Marconi and Hunt 2003).

On the basis of following explanation we conclude the hypothesis that

Ho: Company image does not have a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

H2: Company image has a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

Company Reputation

The third sub-construct is the company reputation, which refers to the impression of the company's key qualities and "which concentrates on what a company does and how it carries on" (Balmer, Greyser et al. 2002). It is likewise characterized as the level of trust in an association's capacity to fulfill clients' desires on a given trait (Nguyen and Leblanc 2001). The word "reputation" is characterized in Britannica (2010) as the "in general quality or character as seen or judged by individuals" and as the "acknowledgement by other individuals on company trademark or capacity".

A few segments in the manufacturing business, particularly automobile companies depend intensely on their company reputation to pull in and hold their consumers (Nguyen and Leblanc 2001). Truth be told, this study accepts that just about all retailers in the business sector today paying little respect to what products they are offering are intrigued to create and safeguard their separate company reputation. The study done by Nguyen and Leblanc (2001) found that the clients are more slanted to buy the products and services from organizations that they saw as having ideal reputation among their rivals. Fombrun and Van Riel (1997) He focused on that a decent company reputation would improve benefit on the grounds that great reputation would pull in consumers to products, draw in financial specialists to securities, and pull in workers to do their employments legitimately. Purchasers need to know all the more about the organization's products, as well as about the organization itself. Balmer and Gray (2003) He contends that the company's reputation can impact the readiness of purchasers to either give or withhold help from the organization and its products.

As per Gupta and Pirsch (2006), a general uplifting character around the organization brings about a more ideal reaction to consumer relationship management. Conversely, advertising correspondence from organizations with a bad reputation is frequently found to get low consumer help, and can sometimes even blowback (Yoon, Byeon et al. 2007). Organizations with a decent reputation have a more prominent capacity to maintain and hold an above normal profit for resources (Roberts and Dowling 2002) As per (Yoon, Byeon et al. 2007), a great reputation can bring a few advantages to an organization, in the same way as an enhanced image or a capacity to be better arranged for a potential emergency. A decent reputation can likewise lead purchasers to loyal through a purchase as positive for the organization. Consumers' purchasing choices are significantly affected by some un-balanced components. Consumers act in light of stories and rumors when picking which automobile to purchase, they are also impacted by marketing of products, Individuals follow up on observations, not via calculations about the target peculiarities of the products themselves, and these observations are vigorously affected by our own incredibly individual, enthusiastic, non-rational responses to products that are shown to us by organizations, columnists or companions (Van Riel and Fombrun 2007).

An organization with a solid reputation has trustworthiness; it is dependable, responsible, capable what's more quality-cognizant (Ettenson and Knowles 2008). Organizations nowadays get to be extremely delicate about their reputation more than image on the grounds that reputation has more profundity. Reputation is a judgment from the business sector which needs to be protected. Regardless, reputation has ended up maxim, as saw by the yearly overviews on the most regarded organizations that are presently made in very nearly all nations on Fortune's. The most persisting reputations are molded by the enthusiastic bonds between the organization and consumers. It is likewise influenced by monetary execution, the work environment, the nature of products and services, company administration, and vision. The organization picture is influenced adversely or decidedly however every client contact. Was it the organization truck, site or simply a telephone call (Ward, Alsop et al. 2004). Reputations take years to structure yet they can be destroyed in a moment. In this manner you must be concerned of every single client contact and their quality. It is crucial to know whether your organization has any reputation whatsoever, and provided that this is true, what sort of a reputation it is. For a fruitful business it is essential to have a decent reputation (Araújo, Marcon et al. 2002). Balmer and Gray

(2003) argue that a favorable company reputation helps in making consumers' loyalty to the organization and enhances the number of purchases from the company.

On the basis of following explanation we conclude the hypothesis that

H₀: Company reputation does not have a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

H₃: Company reputation has a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

Company Loyalty

Company loyalty is described as a "mental state created by a singular's discernments, convictions and feelings which incite the eagerness or the proposition of creating and keeping up a steady and solid relationship" (Corral, González-Conejero et al. 2000). Oliver, Rust et al. (1997) It demonstrates that an increment in clients' fulfillment stimulates an increment in their devotion to the firm and that this faithfulness prompts an increment in their purchases from the company. Initially, there should be a clear difference between company loyalty and brand loyalty. Company loyalty can prompt buyer loyalty for all the products of the organization Bhattacharya and Sen (2003). The inverse case is not generally genuine.

Iglesias, Singh et al. (2011) He conceptualize company loyalty instead of a consumer's just purchase intent is modeled as the definitive dependent variable for the long life of any organization. Company loyalty is usually considered as element consisting of both a behavioral and an attitudinal dimension Atilgan, Aksoy et al. (2005) and thus not only refers to consumers' future purchasing behavior but also to a certain degree of a deeply held loyalty which stimulate consumers to resist situational influences that might have influence to cause brand switching behaviors of consumers. Therefore organization put their efforts to build strong loyalty of their consumers as it yields future purchases (Gommans, Krishnan et al. 2001). The effect of loyalty on organizations' business exercises are accounted for in numerous studies. (Bettencourt 1997) demonstrate that an increase in consumer's satisfaction gives an increment in their loyalty to the firm and that this loyalty prompts an increment in their buys from the organization. It has been demonstrated that the organizations with a high rate of committed consumers have a genuine preference for products against the competitors (Mellen, Gao et al. 2008).

Company brand loyalty means the strength in the products of the company to attract the consumers towards under the presence of compatible substitute company products (Florek and Insch 2008). Company brand loyalty can be measured by seeing the repurchased intentions of the consumers of a specific company brand products. Presently company brand loyalty is important as it leads to make more committed consumers that have willingness to purchase the specific company products again and again (Sivagnanasundaram, Broman et al. 2004). Consumer loyalty is characterized as the consumer's aim to buy the product and proceed utilizing the brand by re-purchasing. It just means repurchasing of products of a certain company (Rock, Gramm et al. 1994). Consumer's loyalty implies the base requirement for changing to an alternate substitute of the product of the company (Thornberry, Bull et al. 1992).

Consumer's company loyalty is the foundation of sound financial position of any organization as it leads to more purchases from the company (Fisk, Brown et al. 1993). Iniesta and Sanchez (2002) report that loyalty has turned into a significant goal for some companies since it can be utilized as a key variable, for example, in business division. The information of the consumer's profiles for each one level of loyalty would empower the firm to plan separated promoting projects that intend to either keep up and expand loyalty or acquire the loyalty of the individuals who are not yet focused on the firm (Sánchez-Fernández and Iniesta-Bonillo 2006). Balmer, Mukherjee et al. (2006) He stated that both satisfaction and image may have a solid effect on consumer holding (i.e. consumer loyalty to the organization) which thusly may influence the organization's incomes and benefits. Bhattacharya and Sen (2003) He contends that company loyalty is made from the company image and notoriety and the consumers' observations and convictions about important organization characteristics.

On the basis of following explanation we conclude the hypothesis that

Ho: Company loyalty does not have a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

H4: Company loyalty has a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

Company Social Responsibility

Traditionally, organizations need to concentrate on methods for their business operations and their benefits. On the other hand, late advancements in strategic thinking support the need to add activities that swell out from the company to the society. Researchers have recognized these activities as company social responsibilities (CSR) (Margolis, Elfenbein et al. 2007) It can be observed that organizations have put more consideration and resource to local community, rather than absolutely earning profits (Halal 2000). Du, Bhattacharya et al. (2010) Put forward the CSR concept with consumers as it increases the consumer trust and ultimately increases company sales.

As specified prior company social responsibility has turned into a theme that has gotten a great deal of consideration, particularly in the most recent ten year period and buyer reaction to company social responsibility has been examined with numerous dimensions. A dimension that has begun to increase in amount is buyers' behavior and buys expectations and the impact of company social responsibility activities (Pomeroy and Dolnicar 2009). Consumer's conduct towards the organization alludes to their organization assessment, which means individuals' positive or negative judgment of the organization. Company social responsibilities activities are one variable buyer utilize to assess organizations. Consumers' view of company social responsibility has an immediate impact on organization assessment (Ricks Jr 2005). Company social responsibility battles cause consumers to nearly relate to the organization, prompting more positive organization assessments. This perspective is additionally backed by (Aad, Abajyan et al. 2013), who recommended that a more elevated amount of purchasers' apparent company social responsibility induces a higher assessment of the organization. Consumers' view of company social responsibility has an immediate impact on buy plan (Peloza and Shang 2011).

How buyers' see a CSR movement focused around the company's dedication was too analyzed. Input, strength after some time and consistency are the three elements that created this part of company social responsibility (Marin and Ruiz 2007). It is accepted that how buyers see a socially dependable movement may rely on upon the criticalness of the gift which thusly can lead into how the firm will be assessed by the buyers (Pracejus and Olsen 2004). A recommendation was made by (Ahn, Figlewski et al. 1999) in which it is expressed that a buyer sees a company social responsibility movement depending diverse level of responsibility from the company's side. Recently, researchers have considered further research for company social responsibility examination, for example, the relationship in the middle of company social responsibility and organization execution, and company social responsibility in creating nations. These exploration zones have permitted organization win-win circumstances to be recognized by tolerating that benefits and standards strengthen one another' (Wong 2009). Then again, an organization's long haul targets ought to have positive social and natural impact and mindful collaborations (Wheeler and Elkington 2001).

The positive impacts of company social responsibility on clients' reactions have driven numerous organizations to participate in social mindful exercises to endeavor company social responsibility activities. As a rule, organizations that actualizes company social responsibility exercises can pick up diverse focal points, for example, a more great brand picture and better company notoriety Brammer and Pavelin (2004) however there are cases in which company social responsibility exercises can result in a negative impact and reverse discharge against the company (Gao 2009). However, clients' impression of company social responsibility engagement is not controllable and unsurprising, in this way, the impact of company social responsibility on an organization may not generally be useful. Organizations trust that clients will see the company social responsibility message as being genuine and along these lines assess it absolutely. In the event that clients don't see the message as

truthful, doubt will be produced. Incredulity is one of the principle negative client states of mind towards the company social responsibility message.

On the basis of following explanation we conclude the hypothesis that

Ho: Company social responsibility does not have a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

H5: Company social responsibility has a significant impact on consumer's product preference.

Research Methodology

Research methodology means that choose of right model out of multiple choices of strategy planning and implementing for our study of research. In research methodology different activities perform such as making appropriate variable model, data collecting techniques, and formation of data analysis of correct way of methodology is most important step in this chapter. This chapter shows that which research methodology is taking to develop the research design as well as this chapter enclosed the research problem of the study i.e. how various dimensions of company branding relate with consumer product preference in Pakistan. Research design shows the framework of the data gathering and also analyzing of the data. Research design of this study has following dimension as express causal connection between independent variables with dependent variable. Another dimension of research design keep always in your mind is to gather the data an appropriate number of respondents to generalize their finding easily. Our research based on social survey that to what extent consumers are influenced to prefer their product decisions under the influence of company brand. Our study is qualitative as well as quantitative, qualitative research is that to measure the descriptive analysis as to describe the age, gender, income level etc and quantitative research in known as inferential or empirical study to find the result by using statistical techniques to find the impact and relationship between independent variables with customer product preference.

Variables of the Study

- **Dependent Variable:**

Consumer product preference is the dependent variable of this study.

- **Independent Variables:**

Company name, Company image, Company reputation, Company loyalty, Company social responsibility are the independent variables of this study.

Conceptual Framework

Research Site, Population and Sample

Data collection conducted in Lahore scattered areas by chosen different sectors such as private and government institutes, banks, commercial markets, universities, friends and family members who uses the cars. Car consumers selected as a sample to collect the data in Lahore scattered area to fill the questionnaire and to take the consumer point of view about choosing cars under the influence of company brand and also asked the impact and relationship between independent variables on consumer's product preference. Since last two decades in PAKISTAN, rapidly automobile industry growth better implemented this process. This research study was conducted in scattered areas of Lahore through distributed questionnaires in different sectors such as private or government, Banks and also general business community. A sample of 320 plus respondents was selected in this study. Stratified sampling technique was used in this study which means to divide the population into "strata" and it is the type of simple random sampling.

Instrument development

Questionnaire which is used in our study was adopted from different articles and its validity and reliability was clearly mentioned in these articles and variables reference source are shown in following table 1:

Variables of study	Reference source
Consumer product preference	(Stokburger, Ratneshwar, & Sen, 2012)
Company name	(Nizar, Norizan M.& Heung-Ja Hong 2006)
Company image	(Nizar, Norizan M.& Heung-Ja Hong 2006)
Company reputation	(Nizar, Norizan M.& Heung-Ja Hong 2006)
Company loyalty	(Nizar, Norizan M.& Heung-Ja Hong 2006)
Company social responsibility	(www.Honda,Toyota,Suzuki,Daihatsu.com)

Questionnaires distributed to different consumer of the cars to request to fill the statements and insured that your information which you provided through questionnaire will be kept confidential and used only for research purpose. 320 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Out of which 288 questionnaire were fully completed in all respects. 22 were not returned and respondent refused to take the questionnaire and 10 were uncompleted. So 90% was the response rate of the total distributed questionnaires.

SPSS 16.0 was used for measuring the statistical analysis. Descriptive analysis, correlation and regression analysis will be run with the help of questionnaire by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science).

Analysis and Interpretation

In this chapter of research article; data collection method, instrument, research procedure and analysis of its results between independent variables and dependent variables and also its relationship and distribution of the questionnaires among consumers of the automobiles discussed. Research questionnaire used as 5 point likert scale and entered into statistical software of SPSS and run the descriptive analysis, correlation and regression analysis. The reliability of results through data collection by questionnaires is .897 while the factor wise reliability of questions is given in the following table 2

Factors	Reliability
Company Name	.748
Company Image	.727
Company Reputation	.773
Company Loyalty	.677
Company Social Responsibility	.828

Descriptive analysis

Following is the descriptive analysis of all the respondents regarding their responses of the questions in questionnaire.

Table3- Demographic Profile of Respondents

Category	Classification	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender	Male	228	79.2
	Female	60	20.8
Qualification	Matric	20	6.9
	Intermediate	57	19.8
	Graduation	108	37.5
	Masters	87	30.2
	Others	16	5.6
Income Level	Less than 50,000	36	12.5
	50,000-60,000	83	28.8
	60,001-70,000	54	18.8
	70,001-80,000	53	18.4
	80,001 to above	62	21.5
Age in Years	20 or less	20	6.9
	21 to 25	26	9.0
	26 to 30	48	16.7
	31 to 35	72	25.0
	36 to 40	83	28.8
	Above 40	39	13.5

Table4- Descriptive Statistics of respondents

Variables of Study	Response of Respondent In Numbers				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Indifference	Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel a strong sense of belonging to this car	6	33	38	120	91
This car expresses what I believe in	5	35	58	137	53
This car is like a part of me	8	49	48	101	82
This car has a great deal of personal meaning for me	-	38	64	108	78
I identify strongly with this car	12	34	63	114	65
Company Name					
The name of the company manufactures the car is well known	12	26	68	100	82
The car carries the name of the company	8	42	57	117	64
The car carries both company name and its generic name	12	46	76	97	57
The company uses its name to all the cars it produces	16	47	68	116	41

The company use different brand name for cars it produces	13	58	60	113	44
Company Image					
The company is advanced and inventive.	4	39	56	135	54
The company is successful and self-confident.	8	33	60	105	82
The company is leading and sharp.	8	44	61	83	92
The company does business in an ethical way.	9	26	67	96	90
The company is open and responsive to consumers.	40	39	23	105	81
Company Reputation					
The company manufactures car has an emotional attraction to me.	8	13	72	131	64
The company which manufactures the car is known for its high quality products.	24	20	62	109	73
The company which manufactures the car is the auto-mobile industry leader.	24	20	62	109	73
The company which manufactures the car is a good workplace environment.	-	31	22	126	109
The company which manufactures the car has a high financial position.	8	18	18	110	134
Company Loyalty					
This car model is only offered by the company that I used to utilize.	4	30	59	120	75
The company which offers the car is overtaking its competitors.	11	38	47	111	81
I have a affection and strong attachment to this company.	10	47	45	104	82
I have high regard to company car.	14	39	60	105	70
I always use company's cars.	9	36	87	96	60
Company Social Responsibility					
The company produces environmental friendly cars.	9	42	50	101	86
The company conducted free seminars regarding road safety.	5	44	61	98	80
The company has planted trees to reduce the pollution.	13	34	47	125	69
The company has established free medical camps in flood affected areas of Pakistan.	8	31	68	87	94
The company runs free schools to increase literacy rate in country.	7	37	58	130	56

Table 5- Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Consumer product preference	288	3.7	0.8084
Company name	288	3.5	0.7703
Company image	288	3.6	0.7885
Company reputation	288	3.9	0.7544
Company loyalty	288	3.6	0.7198
Company social responsibility	288	3.7	0.8353

Table5 provides descriptive statistics for the variables through consumer product preferences, company name, company image, company reputation, company loyalty and company social responsibility. In this above table, “N” represents the number of respondents, and means represent the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable and standard deviation shows the deviation of actual results from expected once.

Inferential Analysis

Co-relation

Correlation analysis means a relationship between dependent variable with one or more independent variables. Normally the range of correlation coefficient is one (1 Positive, negative). Positive correlation means that a change in independent variable that impact on dependent variable identical way. In negative correlation, change in independent variable that impact on dependent item identical but in opposite way.

TABLE 6- Co-Relation Analysis

	Consumer product preference	Company name	Company image	Company reputation	Company loyalty	Company social responsibility
Consumer product preference	1	---	---	---	---	---
Company name	.749**	1	---	---	---	---
Company image	.749**	.697**	1	---	---	---
Company reputation	.604**	.619**	.692**	1	---	---
Company loyalty	.274**	.226**	.218**	.220**	1	---
Company social responsibility	.217**	.046	.052	.015	.348**	1

This research study analyze the correlation between independent items with dependent variable is positive correlated with (.01) and (.05) significantly as shown in above table of correlation matrix which is derived from our SPSS file. Hypothesis between dependent and independents items are positively significant. This study consist other independent items remain constant the change in “company name” of one unit will affect (.749**) positively on “consumer product preference” as dependent item. Other independent variables remain constant the change in “company image” of one unit impact (.749**) significantly on “consumer product preference”. Other independent variables remain constant the change in “company reputation” of one

unit impact (.604**) significantly on “consumer product preference”. By other independent items remain constant the change in “company loyalty” of one unit will change the dependent variable “consumer product preference” as (.274**) significantly. Dependent variable “consumer product preference” changes (.217**) positively with (0.01) level significantly by changing of independent item of “company social responsibility” of one unit and when other indicators remain constant.

Regression

Linear regression attempts to model the impact between two variables by fitting a linear equation to observed data. One variable is considered to be an explanatory variable, and the other is considered to be a dependent variable.

Table 7

Variable	B	R Square	Adj R Square	Sig
Company name	.786	.561	.560	.000

Table 7 shows that the regression analysis between company name and dependent variable of consumer product preference. R2 is the multiple correlation coefficients, is .561 and Adjusted R2 is .560, meaning that 56.1% variance in consumer product preference through company name signifies the regression coefficient i.e. Beta (β) of company name with consumer product preference is .786 with the significant value.000 which shows a positive and significant relationship between company name and consumer product preference.

Table 8

Variable	B	R Square	Adj R Square	Sig
Company image	.768	.561	.559	.000

Table 8 shows that the regression analysis between company image and dependent variable of consumer product preference. R2 is the multiple correlation coefficients, is .561 and Adjusted R2 is .559, meaning that 56.1% variance in consumer product preference through company image and signifies the regression coefficient i.e. Beta (β) of company name with consumer product preference is .768 with the significant value.000 which shows a positive and significant relationship between company image and consumer product preference.

Table 9

Variable	B	R Square	Adj R Square	Sig
Company reputation	.648	.365	.363	.000

Table 9 shows that the regression analysis between company reputation and dependent variable of consumer product preference. R2 is the multiple correlation coefficients, is .365 and Adjusted R2 is .363, meaning that 36.5% variance in consumer product preference through company reputation and signifies the regression coefficient i.e. Beta (β) of company reputation with consumer product preference is .648 with the significant value.000 which shows a positive and significant relationship between company reputation and consumer product preference.

Table 10

Variable	B	R Square	Adj R Square	Sig
Company loyalty	.308	.075	.072	.000

Table 10 shows that the regression analysis between company loyalty and dependent variable of consumer product preference. R2 is the multiple correlation coefficients, is .075 and Adjusted R2 is .072,

meaning that 7.5% variance in consumer product preference through company loyalty and signifies the regression coefficient i.e. Beta (β) of company with consumer product preference is .308 with the significant value.000 which shows a positive and significant relationship between company loyalty and consumer product preference.

Table 11

Variable	B	R Square	Adj R Square	Sig
Company social responsibility	.211	.047	.044	.000

Table 11 shows that the regression analysis between company social responsibility and dependent variable of consumer product preference. R2 is the multiple correlation coefficients, is .047 and Adjusted R2 is .044, meaning that 4.7% variance in consumer product preference through company social responsibility and signifies the regression coefficient i.e. Beta (β) of company with consumer product preference is .211 with the significant value.000 which shows a positive and significant relationship between company social responsibility and consumer product preference.

Multiple Regression

By applying multiple regressions in the model we see that over all co-efficient of determination R-square value is .694 which shows that the overall independent variables have impact on consumer product preference by 69.4%.

In contrast to simple regression, in multiple regression model in table 12 shows the three parameters of company branding i.e. company name, company image, company social responsibility have significant impact on dependent variable consumers' product preference as their significance values are .000 and their weights as values of Beta are .441, .413, and .164 respectively. While two parameters of company branding i.e. company reputation, and company loyalty does not have significant impact on consumers' product preference as their level of significance are .217 and .586 respectively and their values of Beta are .063 and .022.

Table 12- Multiple Regression

Dependent variable	Parameters	Beta	Standard Error	Significance
Consumer product preference	Company name	.441	.050	.000
	Company image	.413	.053	.000
	Company reputation	.063	.051	.217
	Company loyalty	.022	.041	.586
	Company social responsibility	.164	.034	.000

Multi colinearity Test

Multi collinearity is regression diagnostics test which is applied to check the collinearity present between the independent variables of the given model. By applying this diagnostics test the values of variance inflation factor (VIF) is below 10 which shows there is no colinearity between predictor variable.

Table 13- Multicollinearity Test

Independent variables	Variance inflation factor	Tolerance
Company name	2.103	.476
Company image	2.481	.403
Company reputation	2.082	.480
Company loyalty	1.216	.822
Company social responsibility	1.144	.874

In the given table the values of VIF for all the variables are less than 10 as company name, company image, company reputation, company loyalty and company social responsibility has 2.103, 2.481, 2.082, 1.216 and 1.144 respectively.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Our endeavor and outcomes of this research study are describing in conclusions chapter. This study was based on independent variables affecting to the dependent variable such as company name, company image, company reputation, company loyalty and company social responsibility with consumer product preference and also its effect on it. With the help of questionnaire relating our variables were conducted the study and extract the result by using statistical tool and techniques. This study improves the involvement of the cars using consumer relating decision behavior process.

Table 14- Hypothesis Testing

No	Hypotheses	Result supported
H ₁	Company name has significant Impact on consumer product preference	Accepted Table7, Table12
H ₂	Company image has significant Impact on consumer product preference	Accepted Table8, Table12
H ₀	Company reputation does not have significant Impact on consumer product preference	Rejected Table12
H ₀	Company loyalty does not have significant Impact on consumer product preference	Rejected Table12
H ₅	Company social responsibility has significant Impact on consumer product preference	Accepted Table11, Table12

H₁: Company name has significant impact on consumer product preference.

Company name has significant relationship and impact on consumer product preference with (.749**) Pearson value of correlation, regression coefficient value Beta (β) is .786, R Square is .561, it means that consumer product preference is expected to increase by .561 if company name increase by 1 and significant value is lesser than .05 ($P < .05$) that shows company name has positive impact on dependent variable and supported through table 4.39.

H₂: Company image has significant impact on consumer product preference

Company image has significant relationship and impact on consumer product preference with (.749**) Pearson value of correlation, regression coefficient value Beta (β) is .768, R Square is .561, it means that consumer product preference is expected to increase by .561 if company image increase by 1 and significant value is lesser than .05 ($P < .05$) that shows company image has positive impact on dependent variable and supported through table 4.40.

H₀: Company reputation does not have significant impact on consumer product preference

Although Company reputation has relationship with consumer product preference with (.604**) Pearson value of correlation, linear regression coefficient value Beta (β) is .648, R Square is .365, it means that consumer product preference is expected to increase by .365 if company loyalty increase by 1 and significant value is lesser than .05 ($P < .05$) that shows company loyalty has positive impact on dependent variable and supported through table 4.41 but by combining all the parameters of company branding on consumer product preference in multiple regression the company reputation does not show significant impact on consumer product preference as shown in table 4.44.

H₀: Company loyalty does not have significant impact on consumer's product preference

Although company loyalty has relationship with consumer product preference with (.274**) Pearson value of correlation, linear regression coefficient value Beta (β) is .308, R Square is .072, it means that consumer product preference is expected to increase by .072 if company loyalty increase by 1 and significant value is lesser than .05 ($P < .05$) that shows company loyalty has positive impact on dependent variable and supported through table 4.42 but by combining all the parameters of company branding on consumer product preference in multiple regression the company loyalty does not show significant impact on consumer product preference as shown in table 4.44.

H₅: Company social responsibility has significant impact on consumer product preference

Company social responsibility has significant relationship and impact on consumer product preference with (.217**) Pearson value of correlation, regression coefficient value Beta (β) is .211, R Square is .047, it means that consumer product preference is expected to increase by .047 if company social responsibility increase by 1

and significant value is lesser than .05 ($P < .05$) that shows company social responsibility has positive impact on dependent variable and supported through table 4.43.

Recommendations and suggestions

- This research study focused only consumer behavior, selecting criteria of consumer and discussed the factors that are relating to consumer product preference while the other perspective of manufacturer ignored in this study.
- This research study consist only five variables discussed by getting different past researches that explained the only consumer product preference strategy or planning and other expects of variables excluded from this research work.
- With the help of this study, impact of company branding dimension on consumer product preference, consumers attained the knowledge about car buying criteria but in this study few factors relating to company branding focused so in future other researcher will be focus on other variables of the automobile industry.

Limitations

There are some limitations which are as follow:

- In this study small sample was used due to time and cost constraint. The results of smaller sample size may differ from large size sample. Due to small size of sample the reliability, validity and generalizability of results are limited.
- The other limitation of this study is that only five dimensions of company branding: company name, company image, company reputation, company loyalty and company social responsibility investigated. Similarly, other dimensions of company brands that impact consumer product preference can also be investigated. For instance company performance, company advertisement package, company awareness is not studied.
- Survey questionnaire was used in this study to collect data from respondents. Any other method can be used to get more authentic information like direct interviews.
- Another limitation of this study was heterogeneity found in gender of respondents because the male respondents (79.2%) are more than female respondent (20.8%).

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